

Reaction pathways during fluid-rock interactions: from laboratory experiments to implications for the crust of the Earth

Lorena H. Filiberto¹, Christine V. Putnis^{1,2}, Andrew Putnis^{1,3}

¹Institut für Mineralogie, University of Münster, 48149 Münster, Germany

²School of Molecular and Life Sciences, Curtin University, Perth, 6845, Australia

³School of Earth and Planetary Sciences, Curtin University, Perth, 6845, Australia

Fluid pathways and their influencing factors in hydrothermal conditions at 200°C have been investigated conducting experiments using cube samples of monomineralic rocks formed by either calcite or plagioclase, and different types of solutions. Analytical techniques, including SEM, Raman Spectroscopy, AFM, and Electron Microprobe, were used to analyze fluid-induced reactions. Results show three possible reactions pathways: (1) Mg-carbonates replace calcite along the sides of the cubes when using a seawater solution; (2) hydroxylapatite and albite replace calcite and labradorite through the grain boundaries, when using a 0.1M Na₂HPO₄ solution and a Na-silicate solution, respectively; and (3) a combination of both when hydroxylapatite replaces calcite using a 1M Na₂HPO₄ solution. We present a model based on the combination of experimental observations and PhreeqC simulations to highlight the importance fluid volume's availability in a grain boundary versus in the bulk solution and the formation of interconnected porosity during mineral replacements. Such factors play an important role in the kinetics and relative solubilities of rock systems by changing the conditions at the interfacial fluid–mineral boundary layer that will determine initial dissolution or precipitation and whether the supersaturation of a product phase is reached.

Linking the outcomes of our experimental investigations and interpretations based on our models to a natural geological setting is essential for advancing our understanding of fluid-rock interactions. To draw this connection, we have investigated granulitic to amphibolitic anorthosites from the island of Krossøy, in the northern part of the Bergen Arcs, Norway. Despite variations in conditions, the mechanisms and processes observed in our experiments might be influencing in these metamorphic rocks as well. This study might contribute to the understanding the complex geological dynamics of the Bergen Arcs, the rheology in the lower-mid crust and the development of shear zones.